

From trust levels to trust types: How media use shapes political trust

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Abstract

An extensive strand of literature demonstrates that citizen evaluations of political institutions that serve as the foundation for political trust judgments are frequently formed based on mediated political information obtained from news media channels. Despite the richness of the literature, two conceptual limitations persist. First, many studies operationalize media influence as a direct relationship between exposure to specific media sources and trust. Second, political trust itself is often operationalized as a unidimensional outcome – an aggregated index of confidence in political institutions. The present study addresses these gaps by proposing an integrated, two-stage heuristic model of media influence on political trust. On the predictors side, the paper distinguishes between media consumption patterns that capture structural conditions under which political information reaches the users, and media-related attitudes that determine how incoming information is evaluated and processed. On the outcome side, the analysis moves focus from the influence of media on political trust level to the normative interpretation and foundations that underly the political trust judgement where a distinction is made between skeptical, cynical and compliant trust types. The findings show that media predictors operate differently across these two outcomes. Trust in media and perceived media impartiality are consistent positive predictors of the aggregated political trust index, suggesting that confidence in the information environment is closely linked to institutional confidence. However, the trust-type models reveal a more ambivalent pattern. Traditional media use and positive media evaluations reduce cynical mistrust but mainly strengthen compliant rather than skeptical trust. By contrast, sustained exposure to political news increases the likelihood of skeptical trust, whereas reliance on multiple information sources strengthens cynical mistrust and weakens both skeptical and compliant trust. Skeptical trust therefore does not appear to emerge from a general spillover of social trust or from confidence in media as a heuristic shortcut. Rather, it is more closely associated with cognitive resources and sustained political information exposure. The findings suggest that media do not only affect how much citizens trust political institutions, but also whether such trust reflects a skeptical, compliant, or cynical judgement.

Keywords

Political trust; trust judgments; media trust; media malaise; virtuous circle; skeptical trust; Europe

Introduction

Over the past few years, the erosion of political trust, interpreted as an aggregated quantitative decline of public confidence in political authorities, has become a central concern in debates about the state of contemporary democracies. Yet, the democratic meaning of this erosion is not self-evident: lower trust might signal public disengagement and delegitimation, but it can also reflect critical scrutiny of poorly performing institutions. An extensive body of literature documents declining or persistently low levels of trust in government, parliament, political parties and other representative political institutions across established democracies in the European Union (EU) and beyond (Van der Meer, 2017; Citrin et al., 2018; Valgarðsson et al., 2025).

Major political and economic disruptions, including the global financial crisis, the Eurozone crisis, the migration crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, and most recently Russia's war in Ukraine have been widely examined in relation to the conditions under which citizens maintain, revise, or withdraw confidence in political institutions (Armingeon & Guthmann, 2014; Torcal, 2014; Foster & Frieden, 2017; Dennison & Geddes, 2019; Devine et al., 2021; Schraff, 2021). The decline of public trust is not merely a shift in attitudes; this process has been linked to growing support for anti-establishment and populist actors, electoral volatility, and reduced institutional compliance among others. Given the important role attributed to political trust as an instrument of legitimacy and as a tool of governmental accountability, dynamics of trust levels and factors that contribute to positive or negative shifts in public trust are of theoretical and policy relevance.

Among the numerous predictors, media occupy a special place in the political trust discourse. With the exception of occasions of direct interaction of citizens with political actors and institutions—such as voting in an election, signing a petition, meeting a local council representative or a mayor, or participation in demonstration—which are either relatively infrequent or often exercised by only a minority in society, traditional news media and digital news platforms constitute primary sources of information about the political system for the public. Daily reports about political events, new policies adopted, accomplishments of the government, unfolding scandals and other political topics that are used by citizens to inform their perceptions of political institutions, assess their trustworthiness, and ultimately decide about trust, are acquired through media. Serving as core mediators of political information, news media therefore become important agents of public trust-building or trust erosion.

Empirical research increasingly shows that the nature and duration of exposure to media as well as the qualitative characteristics of media environments are associated with variation in political trust – both at the within-country and cross-national levels. The findings, however, are heterogenous. First, the type of media has proven to introduce substantial variation in confidence in institutions (Memoli, 2020; Strömbäck et al., 2016; Fletcher & Park, 2017). Comparative studies indicate that public service broadcasting and legacy news appear to be positively associated with institutional trust (Aalberg & Curran, 2012; Strömbäck et al., 2016). At the same time, extensive reliance on digital media and social media often exhibits negative associations with public trust (Kiratli, 2023; Ceron, 2015). Furthermore, macro-level features of media systems, such as media pluralism, presence or absence of censorship and regulatory safeguards, have also shown to condition the relationship between media and trust in institutions (Hanitzsch et al., 2018; Norris, 2011).

Despite the richness of the literature, two conceptual limitations persist. First, the political trust crisis discourse often omits the normative dimension of trust. Across many contributions, political trust is often operationalized as a unidimensional outcome – an aggregated index of confidence in political institutions. However, a political trust measure based on the respondent's subjective

assessment of reliability of political actors and institutions largely captures the surface level of support or distrust. What it does not reveal is whether the reported trust level reflects an informed skeptical evaluation of institutional performance, habitual uncritical compliance with the authorities, or generalized wholesale cynicism. In other words, similar levels of reported trust may rest on very different foundations and therefore have different implications for democratic accountability.

This distinction becomes essential from the perspective of the role political trust plays in a democratic political system. On the one hand, greater amount of public trust fosters compliance and law-abiding behavior, allowing governments to exercise authority without excessive reliance on coercion (Levi & Stoker 2000; Hetherington 2005). On the other hand, democratic governance equally depends on citizens' capacity for critical scrutiny. Hence, skepticism becomes central as a performance-responsive attitude that supports sanctioning without collapsing into wholesale delegitimation that comes with corrosive cynicism (Rosanvallon, 2008; Norris 2011). Skeptical trust is therefore theorized as conducive to democratic governance precisely because it conditions confidence on evidence and institutional safeguards and thus represents an effective mechanism of justified support and accountability (Norris, 2022). To address the normative quality of political trust in contemporary democracies, the paper investigates and compares models of an aggregated trust measure and a typology of trust judgements. By comparing models of national political trust and types of trust judgement, the paper examines which media-related factors are associated with citizens' trust, and whether media are associated with skeptical, compliant, or cynical trust judgements.

Second, many studies examine media influence as a direct relationship between exposure to specific media sources and trust, without differentiating between dimensions and elements of media engagement. This approach risks obscuring the distinct ways in which information enters and is processed during the evaluative process. It remains insufficiently clear whether media matter mainly because they structure access to political information, because they affect the credibility attributed to this information, or because these two processes operate jointly. The paper therefore distinguishes between three analytically different media-related dimensions: the macro-level information environment, individual media consumption patterns, and attitudes toward media. More specifically, the paper asks whether these factors operate similarly for aggregated national trust and for different types of trust judgement, or whether distinct media conditions are linked to skeptical, compliant, and cynical forms of trust.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 1 provides a literature review. Section 2 presents the heuristic model and formulates the hypotheses. Section 3 describes data and measurement. Section 4 presents and discusses the empirical findings on the relationship between media environments and political trust across 24 European countries. Conclusions summarize the findings.

Literature review: Media and political trust

Mediated political information and attitude formation. A useful starting point for theorizing the media-trust link is Zaller's Receive-Accept-Sample (RAS) model, which treats political attitudes as formed through engagement with political messages, their acceptance or rejection, and the selective retrieval of available considerations when citizens express an opinion (Zaller, 1992). The important contribution of the RAS-model is that it separates three analytically distinct stages in opinion formation: whether citizens receive political information in the first place, whether they treat these messages as credible and accept them, and which from the multiple considerations become available at the moment when an opinion is expressed. Applied to political trust, this perspective suggests that trust and evaluation of trustworthiness are not simply reflections of institutional performance: they are

mediated by the content and structure of information flows in society. Media, in turn, matter not only because they transmit and disseminate political information, but because they affect which messages become available, credible, and salient when citizens evaluate political actors and institutions. The same amount of exposure to media news can therefore be positively or negatively associated with political trust, depending on whether it increases contact with substantive political information, repetitive scandal, government-controlled narratives among the other. The media malaise and the virtuous circle perspectives extend this logic by elaborating how media type, intensity of exposure, and media environment structure the political information available to citizens.

Media malaise: negativity, cynicism, and erosion of trust. The media malaise theory posits that the presentation of political information, foremost in television news, tends to be unbalanced. Two specific features are underscored as being at the heart of the “malaise” mechanism. First, the persistence of negativity and conflict in the news media, including the prevalence of topics such as scandals, incompetence, and lack of integrity. Secondly, the presentation of politics as “strategic game” or “horse race” that concentrates attention on tactics, polls, and winning strategies rather than on policy or other substantive issues (Patterson, 1993; Cappella & Jamieson, 1997; Aalberg et al., 2012). Both these features of news reporting, when recurring repeatedly and extensively, can prime citizens to perceive political actors and institutions as predominantly self-serving, corrupt, and unresponsive, which in turn leads to a decline of political trust and political engagement in society on the one hand, and to growing apathy and cynicism on the other (Robinson, 1976; Cappella & Jamieson, 1997; de Vreese, 2005).

The media malaise thesis was actively tested in the European context, where only partial confirmation was found, while blanket claims that “more news always leads to less trust” were largely rejected (Newton, 1999; Norris, 2000; de Vreese, 2005; Luengo & Maurer, 2009). More specifically, the literature underscores several nuances in the operation of the malaise mechanism. First, the effect of news content is not uniform, as pre-existing individual conditions such as political interest, political knowledge, education, and financial status, among others, shape how audiences interpret and respond to negative news (De Vreese & Semetko, 2002; Aalberg et al., 2012; Brosius et al., 2019). In particular, malaise effects were found to be absent or less pronounced among individuals with higher education, more political knowledge, and greater interest and engagement with politics (Newton, 1999; Strömbäck et al., 2016). Newton (1999) explained these results by the specifics of European news systems, which aim to inform rather than entertain. This results in fostering “critical citizens”, who question political actors, but still support democratic institutions (Norris, 2000, 2011).

Secondly, beyond content-level features (e.g., framing, sensationalism), system-level characteristics of media, such as audience fragmentation and advertising pressure, were found to be associated with lower levels of political trust, net of macroeconomic conditions, government performance, and individual sociodemographic controls (Ariely, 2015; Hallin & Mancini, 2004; Brüggemann et al., 2014). Third, the operation of malaise effects is also conditioned by public confidence in the media sources themselves. When a media source is trusted, consumption of news information is positively associated with political trust. Contrary to this, when the public perceives news media as biased or captured, this mistrust spills over into mistrust toward political institutions (Tsfati & Ariely, 2014; Hanitzsch et al., 2018; Memoli, 2020). Fourth, the type of media matters. Studies that analyze diverse media sources, generally draw a distinction between “traditional” media sources that tend to foster trust and mobilization, and digital and social media that typically deepen cynicism and conspiracy beliefs (Ceron, 2015; Memoli, 2020; Kiratli, 2023; Daminov, 2024). The media malaise effect on political trust, therefore, is not considered an inevitable outcome of news consumption, but

rather an effect conditional on specific structural and institutional characteristics of both the political system and the media environment (Newton & Norris, 2000; Strömbäck et al., 2016). As such, the relationship between negative, framed media news and political attitudes in the European context is frequently framed as a “malaise vs mobilization” dual association (Ejaz, 2017).

Virtuous circle and informed trust. Contrary to the media malaise argument, the virtuous circle thesis posits that news media, by expanding exposure to political information, reinforce political knowledge, engagement, and ultimately strengthen public trust in the political system and institutions (Norris, 2000). The virtuous circle highlights the feedback loop and the reciprocal dynamics of this association. As exposure to news increases interest in politics and the sense of political efficacy among the public, more politically interested citizens in turn consume more news, which further reinforces their political trust. Extensive scholarship has tested the virtuous circle and often found partial confirmation across the EU and more broadly the European continent (Newton, 1999; Norris, 2000; de Vreese & Boomgaarden, 2006; Luengo & Maurer, 2009; Strömbäck et al., 2016).

One of the main empirical findings concerns the diverse effects of media types on political trust. Legacy and information-rich media, such as printed and online editions of quality newspapers, have proven to be more consistently associated with higher institutional trust. By contrast, consumption of news from television, radio, and especially from algorithmically curated and more fragmented digital spaces such as social media platforms reveals weaker, mixed, or negative association with political trust (Luengo & Maurer, 2009; Ceron, 2015; Memoli, 2020; Kiratli, 2023; Daminov, 2024; Verboord et al., 2025). The trust-enhancing effect of media use may occur when citizens encounter professionally produced and politically informative news (Curran et al., 2009; Aalberg & Curran, 2012). A further strand of research shifts attention from media type to content tone and informational depth. Here, previous studies suggest that the effect of media exposure depends not only on frequency of use, but also on whether citizens encounter negative, sensationalized, or high-quality substantive political information. Quality content may increase knowledge and support institutional trust, while strongly negative or crisis-oriented coverage can foster more critical evaluations, with effects again varying across countries (de Vreese & Boomgaarden, 2006; Brosius et al., 2019).

Further findings suggest that media system characteristics play a structural role in enabling the virtuous circle. In particular, the effect of news exposure on political trust depends on the type of media system, the degree of media freedom, and the level of audience fragmentation. For instance, in more fragmented or commercialized media environments, news consumption might not consistently translate into higher trust (Hallin & Mancini, 2004; Brüggemann et al., 2014; Ariely, 2015). On the other hand, in less free media systems the positive association between television exposure and political trust might reflect propaganda-induced support rather than genuine institutional confidence (Zaller, 1992; Knoll et al., 2023). Finally, trust in the media itself emerges as a mediator of the association between news consumption and political trust. When media are perceived as credible and independent, news consumption is more likely to reinforce institutional trust. Where media are perceived as biased, distrust in the media can spill over into distrust toward political institutions (Tsfati & Ariely, 2014; Hanitzsch et al., 2018; Fletcher & Nielsen, 2018; Fletcher et al., 2025). To summarize, past research on media influence on political trust across the European context mainly confirms the virtuous circle thesis, but points to its conditional nature: the virtuous circle is not a universal channel of trust enhancement. Its effects depend on prior political interest, ideological orientation, media trust, and broader patterns of self-selection into news consumption (Strömbäck et al., 2016; Bach et al., 2022; Himmelroos & von Schoultz, 2023).

Theoretical framework

From trust levels to trust types. The present paper addresses two reasons why the core logic, and the evidence concerning the media-political trust association deserve to be revisited which concern the conceptualization and the operationalization of both political trust (outcome) and media (predictor).

First, across many studies examining the influence of media on political attitudes the emphasis is made on aggregate levels of political trust or broad measures of political system support as the main outcome. While this has yielded important insights, these findings leave largely unexamined the normative quality of trust judgments. Although public trust constitutes an important resource for democratic governance, its magnitude alone does not determine its normative significance. High levels of political trust, often widespread also in autocracies, are alone not indicative of democratic quality and thus are not inherently desirable. Likewise, low levels of political trust are not necessarily a sign of democratic crisis and might instead point to malfunctioning institutions. Public trust judgements are not uniform. Express trust may reflect an informed, performance-based assessment of the government and other political institutions. Alternatively, it may also reflect habitual compliance with authorities or a diffuse sense of affective attachment to the country. Importantly, the foundations of political trust judgements provide different implications for the democratic political system: trust based on blind compliance becomes a source of regime support and legitimacy, but fails to meet the accountability criteria, while mistrust rooted in wholesale cynicism can undermine legitimacy without necessarily producing constructive performance-based sanctioning. Consequently, high public trust in a system with poorly performing, corrupt institutions and low trust in a society with well performing political institutions are qualitatively different phenomena, requiring different policy responses. Without distinguishing between the underlying foundations of political trust judgments, the normative implications of media influence also remain ambiguous.

This paper conceptualizes political trust not merely as a level of support or a psychological predisposition, but an evaluative judgment based on the assessment of trustworthiness of political institutions (Levi & Stoker, 2000; Van der Meer & Hakhverdian, 2017; Norris, 2022). This evaluation can be aligned or misaligned with the indicators of trustworthy performance of institutions (understood here as an external analytical benchmark). Drawing on Norris (2022), the typology of trust judgments allows us to differentiate between qualitatively and consequentially distinct forms of trust¹: 1) skeptical trust or mistrust reflecting an evaluation aligned with objective performance of institutions; 2) compliant trust reflecting a positive trust judgment not aligned with and insensitive to the actual performance of institutions; 3) and cynical mistrust that refers to a negative trust judgment not aligned with institutional performance. In this framework, trust is no longer normatively desirable per se. Instead, what matters, is the basis or the foundation on which trust is granted (see Figure 1).

To advance a more differentiated interpretation of media influence on political trust, the model investigates two analytically distinct outcomes: (1) the aggregate level of political trust, measured by the political trust index; (2) an operationalized typology of trust judgements. This approach allows the analysis to ask whether media environments foster confidence as such – or whether they generate democratically preferable forms of political trust. This approach also helps

¹ Norris's original typology distinguishes between skeptical trust and skeptical mistrust depending on whether institutional performance is positive or negative. In the empirical analysis, these two categories are treated jointly as performance-aligned trust judgements, since both indicate correspondence between reported trust and institutional conditions. The distinction between positive and negative institutional performance is retained in the construction of the benchmark but not modelled as a separate outcome category.

reconcile the competing expectations in the media-trust literature. Rather than treating media malaise and virtuous-circle arguments as mutually exclusive claims about whether media exposure fosters or suppresses trust, they may both operate but become visible in different trust outcomes.

Figure 1. Typology of trust judgements.

		Trustworthy performance	
		<i>Positive</i>	<i>Negative</i>
Trust judgment	<i>Positive</i>	Skeptical trust	Compliant trust
	<i>Negative</i>	Cynical mistrust	Skeptical mistrust

Source: Norris, 2022.

Drawing on the media malaise thesis, the virtuous circle thesis, and Zaller's information-flow perspective, we hypothesize that media consumption patterns and attitudes toward media will be associated with both the level and the type of political trust, but not necessarily in the same direction. For example, following the media malaise thesis, more frequent use of online news and social media for political information is likely to be associated with lower aggregate political trust and a higher likelihood of cynical mistrust. Duration of exposure, on the other hand, is anticipated to exhibit an ambivalent pattern – a positive association with both skeptical mis(trust), understood as performance-responsive form of trust judgement, following the virtuous circle logic and the cynical mistrust type, following the malaise thesis. Among the media types, a positive association is expected between the frequent use of legacy media (television, newspapers, radio) and aggregate political trust, following the virtuous circle logic. At the level of trust types, however, the association is anticipated to diverge across sources, with newspapers use expected to be more closely associated with skeptical mis(trust), while television news may be more strongly associated with compliant trust. Finally, perceptions of media—higher media trust, perceived media impartiality, and media literacy—are expected to be associated with higher aggregate political trust and a lower likelihood of cynical mistrust.

A heuristic model of media influence on political trust. Numerous studies examine whether exposure to a particular media type increases or decreases political trust. In these analyses, media use or media exposure is often treated as a relatively direct predictor of trust. However, political trust does not respond immediately to exposure; instead, the mechanism behind media influence on trust is best understood as a two-step mediated evaluation. The present study therefore proposes an integrated, two-stage heuristic model of media influence on political trust. Within this model, institutional performance provides the objective context within which trust judgments can be evaluated, while media shape the political information through which citizens encounter and interpret this performance.

In the first stage, citizens encounter political information. The amount, quality, content and nature of the information depend on three key parameters: (1) the type of media sources used; (2) the diversity of media sources one is exposed to, and (3) the duration of exposure. Each of these parameters captures a different aspect of citizens' informational input. Media types vary in informational depth and quality, editorial control, and susceptibility to strategic framing, sensationalism, fake news, misinformation or echo-chamber effects. From the media malaise perspective, television news, commercial outlets, and social media are more likely to foster distrust and political cynicism, while the virtuous circle literature assigns more positive role to printed

newspapers and professionally regulated broadcast media. Source-specific frequency of exposure therefore serves as a proxy for differential exposure to different information environments (Ceron & Memoli, 2015; Van Aelst et al., 2017; Strömbäck et al., 2013; Tsfati & Ariely, 2014).

Time spent consuming political news constitutes another important indicator of one's engagement with mediated political information. It refers to the quantitative intensity of exposure, or the total amount of time devoted to political content. As such, this indicator reflects the cumulative volume of mediated cues, narratives, and evaluations to which citizens are repeatedly exposed. From the malaise perspective, longer exposure may foster distrust and cynicism when political news is dominated by negativity, scandals and conflicts; from the virtuous circle perspective, sustained contact with political information may instead enhance awareness, political knowledge, and more performance-contingent judgments (Zaller, 1992; Norris, 2000; de Vreese & Semetko, 2002; Prior, 2007). Finally, the concept of media pluralism at the individual level captures the diversity of regularly used sources of political news. In high-choice media environments, individuals who rely on multiple platforms are more likely to encounter heterogeneous perspectives on the same political events, while narrow repertoires and echo chambers may foster attitudinal congruence and amplify distrust. Therefore, use of multiple media sources does not automatically result in higher levels of political trust but can be expected to exhibit meaningful association with the type of trust judgment, in particular skeptical or cynical trust (Van Aelst et al., 2017; Dubois & Blank, 2018; Fletcher & Nielsen, 2018).

In the second stage, the obtained political information is evaluated by the users, when citizens decide which information messages should be integrated into broader judgments about institutional performance and consequently into political trust – and which are disregarded and thus bear no implications for the revision or confirmation of political trust. At the stage of evaluation, importance is attributed to individual cognitive resources and one's perceptions of media. In particular, (1) the perceived credibility of media; (2) the perceived bias, impartiality and autonomy of media; and (3) one's own ability to differentiate between reliable and fake news (i.e. media literacy) are among factors that condition acceptance or rejection of political information.

Existing studies show that trust in news media is closely linked to broader patterns of political trust, perceptions of media bias, political polarization, and satisfaction with democracy (Hanitzsch et al., 2018; Tsfati & Ariely, 2014; van der Meer & Hameleers, 2021; Newman et al., 2022). Perceived impartiality of news media and political information they disseminate also proven highly relevant. Regardless of whether suspicion of media bias is accurate or exaggerated, perceptions of media bias, manipulation, and fake news constitute politically consequential attitudes associated with distrust in political actors and institutions (Egelhofer & Lecheler, 2019; Schulz et al., 2020; Van Duyn & Collier, 2019). Perceived media impartiality therefore functions as a cognitive filter through which mediated political information is accepted, contested, or dismissed. In contrast to media trust or perceived media impartiality, which reflect attitudes about media institutions and political news they disseminate, media literacy refers to individuals' confidence in their own capacity to navigate political information, assess its credibility, and distinguish reliable content from fake news. Within our framework, it operates as an individual resource that conditions how mediated information is interpreted and incorporated into political trust judgments (Jones-Jang et al., 2021; Vraga & Tully, 2021; Guess et al., 2020; Kahne & Bowyer, 2017).

At the individual level, this mechanism is further shaped by characteristics such as education, political interest and civic knowledge which influence the process of information reception, evaluation, and selection. At the macro level, the same mechanism is embedded within the broader media environment, including media freedom, pluralism, censorship, and openness of the information sphere,

which shape the conditions under which political information is produced, circulated, and made available to citizens. Once political information has been received and evaluated, mediated information may have different consequences for political trust judgement. For instance, frequently reliance on weakly curated digital news media, especially combined with perception of media as biased is expected to increase the likelihood of generalized suspicion and cynical mistrust. By contrast, exposure to established media, particularly among citizens with higher civic knowledge and political interest, might support more performance-responsive judgements corresponding to skeptical (mis)trust type (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Integrated model of media environment and political trust formation.

Source: the author.

Data and measurement

To examine the influence of media consumption and perceptions of media on political trust attitudes, data from the TRUEDEM survey conducted in May-July 2025 in 24 European countries is used (Haerper et al., 2026). Within each country, a nationally representative sample of N=1200 permanent residents aged 18 years and above was surveyed, using an online questionnaire in self-completion mode.

Political trust in national institutions. To measure political trust level, an aggregated multi-component index scaled 1-10 and comprising trust attitudes towards eight political institutions is constructed. This includes trust in the national government, the regional government, the national parliament, political parties, the courts and judicial system, the Head of State, the Head of Government, and elections. The selection is based on the theoretically grounded representation of the State featuring both institutional breadth (executive (national government, Head of Government, Head of State), legislative (national parliament, political parties), and judicial (courts and judicial system) branches), and multi-level governance (regional and national governance levels), as well as institutions vs political actors (Head of State, Head of Government). Country-level distributions of the index point to pronounced cross-national differences in both the average level and the distribution of political trust. National mean values vary from 3.86 in Romania and 3.89 in Greece to 6.42 in Denmark and 6.19 in Sweden, yielding a spread of about 2.6 index points (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Political trust index (1-10) distribution by country (%).

Data: TRUEDEM survey on political trust May-July 2025 (N= 24768). The internal consistency of the political trust index scale was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.893.

Typology of trust judgements. While the aggregated trust index captures the level of confidence in national institutions, it does not indicate whether this confidence is normatively aligned with institutional performance (Norris, 2022). For this reason, the second outcome moves from trust level to trust judgement. The typology is constructed by comparing reported (observed) trust with the level of trust that would be expected (predicted) given the objective macro-indicators of institutional performance (Van der Meer & Van Erkel, 2024). The choice of the objective macro performance indicators as the benchmark is motivated by several factors. First, while citizen perceptions of performance expressed through subjective evaluations or satisfaction levels are equally important as predictors of political trust, being of attitudinal nature, they are themselves largely subject to the same influences of mediated political information as the political trust itself. Second, the external consistency approach treats political trust as an evaluative judgement that should bear some relationship to the observable trustworthiness and performance of political institutions. Objective indicators therefore provide an external reference point against which reported political trust can be interpreted, without relying on another attitudinal measure and thus helping to avoid circularity. Third, subjective performance evaluations can be affected by incumbent contamination when performance evaluations capture satisfaction with the current officeholders rather than institutional trustworthiness more generally. Objective indicators help separate long-term institutional conditions from short-term approval/disapproval of the present officeholders. Finally, for their subjective evaluations of institutional trustworthiness, respondents in different countries might use different, country-specific benchmarks making the outcomes hard to compare. Using one and the same set of objective performance indicators therefore enables analysis across 24 countries.

The construction of the typology starts with estimating this expected level of trust, which then serves as the benchmark against which observed trust is evaluated. For this, we employ a two-level linear mixed-effects model with random intercepts specified at the country level. The dependent variable is the aggregated eight-component index of political trust. At level 2, macro indicators of institutional performance and governance quality are included as predictors. Given the limited number

of level 2 units (24 countries), the benchmark relies on a parsimonious specification of macro-level institutional performance. Governance quality is measured using the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), a multidimensional measure that summarizes six dimensions of governance: voice and accountability, political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, and control of corruption. This indicator captures broad structural and institutional conditions under which political trust is normatively expected to vary, including the capacity, integrity, legality, and accountability of public institutions. Economic performance is captured separately through average annual real GDP growth, allowing the benchmark to distinguish governance quality from recent economic performance. Since political trust is widely understood as shaped by sustained institutional performance rather than single-year fluctuations (Levi & Stoker 2000; Van der Meer & Hakhverdian 2017; Van der Meer & Van Erkel, 2024), to make this benchmark less dependent on short-term fluctuations, the averaged values across the 2021–2024 period are used. Importantly, the choice of objective indicators is theoretically guided rather than definitive.

The selection therefore is neither exhaustive nor unique: other dimensions of institutional performance, such as administrative capacity, inequality, or welfare provision, can also be relevant for citizens' trust judgements. Moreover, the choice of objective macro indicators itself affects the predicted trust values and consequently respondents' membership in the typology groups. The purpose of the benchmark is therefore not to establish the complete, "true" or "desired", level of institutional trustworthiness, but to construct a comparable external reference point based on widely used dimensions of performance.

Figure 4. Observed vs. predicted political trust by country.

Data: TRUEDEM survey on political trust, May–July 2025 (N = 24,768). Predicted trust represents the benchmark estimated from the multilevel model including the WGI governance index, average annual real GDP growth over 2021–2024, and individual sociodemographic characteristics. Observed values are the actual mean political trust scores reported by respondents.

At level 1, individual-level sociodemographic characteristics (age, gender, education, and income) are included as controls to account for compositional differences within countries and to avoid attributing demographic differences in baseline trust to institutional performance alone. The model

thus estimates the level of political trust that is statistically predicted by both institutional performance and individual characteristics (see appendix). The regression produces a fitted (predicted) value for each respondent, representing the level of political trust “expected” given the national institutional context and personal attributes. Predicted trust as the benchmark should be interpreted as an externally specified model of institutional trustworthiness, rather than as an ontological measure of the “correct” amount of trust citizens ought to hold. Its function is purely diagnostic: it identifies whether reported trust is broadly consistent with observable institutional conditions or rather departs from them. In this sense, the benchmark does not evaluate whether citizens are right or wrong to express certain level of trust but provides a common reference point against which trust judgements can be interpreted (see Figure 4).

The predicted trust values are used in the second step of the index construction process as a benchmark for identifying deviations (residuals) between predicted and observed political trust. Calculated at the individual level, in substantive terms, these residuals capture whether a respondent exhibits more or less trust than would be expected given the national economic and political conditions of their country as well as individual sociodemographic characteristics. Residuals are standardized to facilitate interpretation and comparability across contexts. Negative residuals indicate lower-than-expected trust relative to the benchmark, while positive residuals indicate higher-than-expected trust. Residuals close to zero, in contrast, indicate that reported trust is broadly aligned with the level predicted by institutional performance and individual characteristics.

In the final step, these standardized residuals are used to distinguish qualitatively different forms of trust judgement. For this, a k-means cluster analysis is applied to the standardized residuals, which groups respondents based on their distance from the predicted trust level while minimizing within-cluster variance. The resulting clusters correspond to three types of trust judgments²: (1) cynical mistrust (residuals from - 2.724 to -0.679) groups individuals whose trust is lower than predicted by institutional performance; (2) skeptical (mis)trust (residuals from -0.679 to 0.517) combines individuals with residuals close to zero, meaning their trust judgments align more or less closely with expected level; and (3) compliant trust (residuals from 0.517 to 3.001) groups respondents with substantially positive residuals, whose trust exceeds what institutional performance would predict. This classification departs from the concept of “trust level” and instead captures the alignment of trust relative to objective institutional conditions. Because the residual-based approach is based on statistical deviation between reported trust and objective institutional performance, the categories should be interpreted as trust judgment types rather than psychological dispositions. The analysis does not capture citizens’ subjective motives, nor does it assume that all respondents in the skeptical category necessarily consciously reason in a skeptical manner. Consequently, the trust types should be interpreted as ideal types or analytical heuristics, rather than as direct measures of citizens’ underlying motives in trust evaluation (Figure 5).

Across the 24 European countries included in analysis, skeptical trust judgments emerge as the most prevalent type accounting for, on average, 42% of the respondents in the pooled sample. Compliant trust judgments are the second most prevalent type, accounting for 31% of the respondents. Finally, the remaining 27% of survey participants were classified as “cynical mistrusters” (see appendix).

² Alternative solutions were explored. The two-cluster solution grouped trust judgements into positive / negative deviations from expected trust, while the four-cluster solution subdivided the cynical and compliant categories into weaker and stronger variants without another substantively distinct trust judgement type. The theoretically expected three-cluster solution provided the most interpretable representation of the underlying structure.

Figure 5. Residual-based typology of political trust judgments.

Notes: K-means cluster analysis ($k = 3$) was applied to standardized residuals to operationalize the theoretically defined trust judgement types. The resulting clusters represent types of trust judgments, based on individual deviations from expected institutional trust and minimized within-cluster variance.

Media exposure and perception. Following the theoretical model, our analytical framework distinguishes six core independent variables – media-related constructs that operationalize various types of associations between media environment and political trust at individual level. The six media-related predictors are structured into two conceptually distinct yet interrelated groups. The first group captures structural patterns of media consumption. It includes individual indicators and indices of (1) media types; (2) duration of exposure to political news through media; and (3) pluralism of media

sources. This cluster of predictors captures the structural conditions under which political news reaches citizens. The second cluster includes individual attitudes about media: (1) trust in media; (2) perceived impartiality of media; and (3) media literacy. This group of predictors captures how incoming political news information is evaluated once it reaches the individual (see appendix).

Individual-level controls. The predictors examining the effect of media consumption patterns and media environment on political trust are complemented by individual-level control variables, including age, gender, settlement type, income, education, left-right ideological position, civic knowledge, interest in politics, and generalized social trust. These controls capture sociodemographic position, political predispositions, cognitive resources, and baseline interpersonal trust, all of which may independently shape political trust and therefore need to be accounted for in the models.

Macro-level data. Beyond individual-level media consumption patterns and media-related attitudes, the model also includes macro-level characteristics of national media systems represented by the World Press Freedom Index to account for structural variation in the information environment across the 24 countries (Reporters Without Borders, 2024). This index provides a comprehensive cross-national assessment of the degree to which journalists operate independently, media outlets function without political or economic interference, and pluralism and transparency are safeguarded within national information systems. Conceptually, the index therefore captures both the structural autonomy and the institutional protection of the media sphere. Given that the dataset comprises only 24 countries at level 2, the number of macro-level predictors is limited to one to avoid overfitting.

Results and discussion

Media influence on aggregate political trust. The first set of models (M1-M4) estimates the association between media-related predictors and the aggregate political trust index: M1 is the baseline model which estimates micro- and macro-level context; M2 captures the structural conditions of information exposure: the type, duration, and diversity of media through which citizens encounter political information; M3 captures the information evaluation stage: trust in and perceptions of media, and media literacy by which mediated information is accepted as credible, impartial, and usable; M4 is an integrated model that includes all groups of predictors (Table 1).

Findings point out that the World Press Freedom Index across all models is systematically positively (0.024-0.048) associated with aggregate political trust, which entails that citizens living in freer media environments report on average higher average trust in national political institutions, net of their media consumption and media perceptions. At the same time, the decline of the coefficient for media environment in M3 after media perceptions are introduced suggests that part of this macro-level effect is connected to citizens' evaluations of the media themselves with citizens in free media environments being more likely to treat mediated political information as credible and impartial.

Given the multi-dimensional nature of the press freedom index, positive association with political trust can be interpreted threefold. First, freer media environments tend to provide citizens with more pluralist information messages, which in turn may foster more balanced evaluations of political actors and political institutions (Newton, 1999; Norris, 2000, 2011; de Vreese, 2005; Strömbäck et al., 2016). This mechanism does not predict a necessarily positive outcome of the public trust judgement but suggests safeguards against the prevalence of both state-sponsored narratives on one hand and wholesale criticism on the other. Secondly, press freedom can also reinforce political trust through accountability. When media have the freedom and capacity to scrutinize political actors and institutions, exposing their failures and misconduct, authorities may appear more restrained and monitorable – and possibly more trustworthy (Rosanvallon, 2008; Levi & Stoker, 2000; Norris, 2022).

Table 1. Multilevel models of media predictors of trust.

		M1 Media Environment	M2 Media Consumption	M3 Media Perceptions	M4 Combined Media
Level 2	World Press Freedom Index	0.048*** (0.006)	0.045*** (0.006)	0.025*** (0.005)	0.024*** (0.006)
	Newspapers (frequency)	–	0.138*** (0.009)	–	0.047*** (0.008)
	Television (frequency)	–	0.199*** (0.009)	–	0.060*** (0.009)
Level 1:	Radio (frequency)	–	0.081*** (0.009)	–	0.030*** (0.008)
Individual Media Consumption Patterns	Online social media (frequency)	–	-0.003 (0.009)	–	-0.028*** (0.008)
	Online websites (frequency)	–	0.034** (0.010)	–	-0.007 (0.009)
	Log (Media Exposure, mins)	–	0.108*** (0.012)	–	0.031*** (0.010)
	Media Pluralism Index (1-10)	–	-0.121*** (0.015)	–	-0.060*** (0.013)
Attitudes and Perceptions about Media	Media Trust Index (1-10)	–	–	0.415*** (0.006)	0.403*** (0.007)
	Media Impartiality Index (1-10)	–	–	0.310*** (0.007)	0.298*** (0.007)
	Media Literacy Index (1-10)	–	–	0.094*** (0.010)	0.102*** (0.010)
Individual Level Controls: Sociodemographic Groups, Cognitive Resources	Age	-0.008*** (0.001)	-0.013*** (0.001)	-0.001*** (0.007)	-0.003*** (0.001)
	Male (ref. female)	0.070** (0.025)	0.038 (0.024)	0.123*** (0.021)	0.098*** (0.021)
	Urban (ref. rural)	0.148*** (0.025)	0.128*** (0.025)	0.078*** (0.021)	0.074*** (0.022)
	Income	0.027*** (0.005)	0.019*** (0.005)	0.022*** (0.004)	0.020*** (0.004)
	Education: medium (ref. low)	-0.049 (0.034)	-0.038 (0.034)	0.004 (0.029)	0.010 (0.030)
	Education: high (ref. low)	0.083** (0.038)	0.106** (0.038)	0.126*** (0.033)	0.137*** (0.033)
	Position on Left-Right Scale	0.059*** (0.005)	0.051*** (0.005)	0.045*** (0.005)	0.044*** (0.005)
	Civic Knowledge	0.038*** (0.012)	0.037*** (0.012)	0.012 (0.010)	0.015 (0.010)
	Interest in Politics	0.307*** (0.015)	0.144*** (0.016)	0.104*** (0.015)	0.077*** (0.015)
	Generalized Social Trust	0.255*** (0.005)	0.233*** (0.005)	0.129*** (0.005)	0.125*** (0.004)

Note. Entries are unstandardized coefficients from linear mixed-effects models estimated by maximum likelihood, with standard errors in parentheses. The dependent variable is the political trust index. Respondents are nested within countries; all models include random intercepts for country. Sample size: N= 24 768. Number of countries = 24 in all models. AIC/BIC values are: M1 = 106,540/106,655; M2 = 104,391/104,562; M3 = 95,636/95,775; M4 = 94,842/95,037. *p < .10, **p < .05, ***p < .001.

Finally, press freedom is closely linked to broader democratic quality of the political system and the overall institutional performance across multiple policy areas, which means that the association with political trust may partly reflect the implications of a wider democratic context (i.e. better performing institutions receive higher levels of public trust), rather than a media-specific effect alone (Brüggemann et al., 2014; Ariely, 2015; Hanitzsch et al., 2018).

In the media consumption model (M2) testing the exposure to various media types, use of majority of media sources is positively associated with political trust index, including television (0.199), newspapers (0.138), radio (0.081), and online news websites (0.034). Duration of exposure to political news is also positively associated with overall political trust (0.108). The observed association is therefore consistent with the virtuous circle thesis expectation that regular contact with political information can reinforce political trust, particularly when information is obtained through established or professionally mediated sources (Newton, 1999; Norris, 2000; de Vreese & Boomgaarden, 2006; Curran et al., 2009; Aalberg & Curran, 2012; Strömbäck et al., 2016). Yet this effect is conditional. Once media evaluations are added in the full model (M4), the coefficients for all media sources become much smaller. Therefore, while legacy media use is associated with higher trust, substantial part of this association seems to be linked to citizens' broader assessment of the media environment, including trust in media and belief in media impartiality. The individual media pluralism index, against the virtuous circle logic, exhibits a negative effect (-0.121 and -0.060) on political trust index in both the media consumption (M2) and the full (M4) models. This finding suggests that use of a wider range of media sources can in fact be associated with exposure to competing, inconsistent, or critical political cues that undermine trust.

Use of social media on the other hand is not statistically significant in the media consumption model (M2) but becomes negatively associated with political trust in the full model (M4). This pattern can be explained through dual effect of social media. On the one hand, social media sites may facilitate direct interaction with politicians through personal posts, likes, comments, messages, and thus reduce the distance between citizens and political elites, which can increase trust (Starke et al., 2020). On the other hand, social media use is also associated with political cynicism through repeated exposure to political attacks and anti-institutional content (Song et al., 2020; Hasell et al., 2025). Therefore, once confidence in media, perceptions of media impartiality, and media literacy are introduced in M4, the remaining association between social media use and political trust becomes negative, consistent with most findings in the field (Ceron, 2015; Memoli, 2020; Kiratli, 2023; Daminov, 2024; Klein & Robison, 2020). Importantly, in M2-M4 social media and online news websites exhibit opposing logics of association with political trust, meaning that digital news exposure should not be treated as uniformly trust-eroding – a distinction already emphasized in previous research (Ceron, 2015; Fletcher & Nielsen, 2018). This suggests that the relevant distinction is not between traditional “offline” and digital “online” media as such, but more between institutionally mediated and editorially curated sources on one hand, and less curated, algorithmically managed social media platforms on the other (Prior, 2007; Van Aelst et al., 2017; Song et al., 2020; Hasell et al., 2025).

The second group of predictors (M3) captures the information evaluation stage of the theoretical model, that is, whether mediated political information is regarded as sufficiently credible to be incorporated into the trust judgement. These variables emerge as the strongest and most consistent predictors of the political trust index. Both in M3 and in the full model M4, trust in media (0.403-0.415) and perceived media impartiality (0.298-0.310) are the largest coefficients estimated, and media literacy (0.094-0.102) is also positively associated with political trust. This pattern indicates that political trust is not formed through access to mediated political information per se. Rather,

political news becomes consequential for political trust when citizens judge the information environment as credible, impartial, and trustworthy, which corresponds to the acceptance stage in Zaller's RAS model (Zaller, 1992). These findings are also consistent with past research showing that confidence in media can "spill over" into political trust, while media mistrust, perceived media bias, or lack of autonomy can interrupt this link (Tsfati & Ariely, 2014; Hanitzsch et al., 2018; Memoli, 2020). This interpretation is also supported by the model-fit statistics: M3 yields a substantially lower AIC (95,636) and BIC (95,775) than M2 (AIC = 104,391; BIC = 104,562). The comparison of M2-M3 model fit, together with the fact that both clusters of predictors retain statistical significance in the full model M4, supports the two-stage model: while exposure structures access to political information, media evaluations largely determine whether this information becomes politically consequential.

Media influence on trust judgment types. While the aggregate trust models largely reproduce patterns documented in previous research, the second set of models (M5-M7) moves from the level of trust to the type of trust judgement and reveals a substantially different picture. Here, the question is not whether media increase or decrease trust in general, but whether they are associated with skeptical, compliant, or cynical forms of political trust. Table 2 presents log-odds coefficients from mixed-effects logistic regressions (not directly comparable in magnitude to M1-M4, and hence the direction of association is mainly under examination). Findings highlight several interesting patterns. First, at the macro level, the press freedom index exhibits positive association with cynical mistrust (0.028) and negative – with compliant trust (-0.031). The association with skeptical (mis)trust is not statistically significant. This pattern suggests that environments with high press freedom and independent media seem to weaken uncritical deference to authority. However, the decline of compliant trust is not accompanied by a corresponding increase in skeptical (mis)trust. Instead, citizens in freer media environments appear more likely to fall into the cynical mistrust category. This finding challenges the optimistic expectation that greater information freedom necessarily promotes more balanced, skeptical, performance-responsive trust judgements. While independent media may enhance citizens' capacity to scrutinize political actors and institutions, exposure to critical information alone does not appear sufficient to generate skeptical trust. Rather, the findings suggest that the erosion of uncritical, compliant trust and the emergence of skeptical, performance-based trust are distinct processes. The findings support the interpretation that democratic accountability depends not only on the availability of critical information through independent media, but also on citizens' capacity to process such information in a differentiated manner (Rosanvallon, 2008; Norris, 2011, 2022).

Among the media consumption patterns, more frequent use of traditional media, such as television, newspapers, and radio, is positively associated with compliant trust judgements (0.032 to 0.055) – and negatively associated with cynical mistrust (-0.029 to -0.095). At the same time, use of traditional media does not necessarily enhance more balanced, skeptical trust judgments: only television news exhibit positive association with skeptical (mis)trust type (0.052). Therefore, rather than fostering skeptical forms of trust, the main effect of traditional media emerges in shifting citizens away from excessive cynicism towards greater institutional confidence. In this context, traditional media emerge as stabilizing mediators, whose role, however, appears more closely linked to the maintenance of institutional legitimacy rather than to the formation of skeptical trust. This finding partly corresponds to the virtuous circle argument that professionally mediated news can sustain institutional confidence (Norris, 2000; Newton & Norris, 2000; Strömbäck et al., 2016). The trust type models further specify this expectation by showing that the trust-enhancing role of traditional media is not normatively uniform. In contrast, frequent use of social media use and online news websites for political information exhibits no significant association with any trust type. Absence of strong effects

challenges the prevalent claim that digital media exposure inherently fuels cynicism or mistrust. At the same time, negative association between social media use and aggregate political trust observed in the previous models suggests that social media use may be associated with lower overall institutional confidence without systematically clustering citizens into cynical, compliant, or skeptical forms of trust.

In addition to media consumption patterns, overall exposure to political news also has distinct implications for trust judgments. Greater exposure to news media is positively associated with skeptical trust (0.044) and negatively – with cynical mistrust (–0.034). Essentially, this implies that cumulative exposure to political news appears to foster more balanced, skeptical evaluations of institutional trustworthiness. Little overall exposure to news, on the other hand, is congruent with cynical judgements. This finding is consistent with the informational logic of the virtuous circle thesis that sustained exposure to political news seems to provide citizens with a broader stock of political information, making trust judgements less likely to collapse into generalized cynicism (Norris, 2000; de Vreese & Boomgaarden, 2006; Strömbäck et al., 2016). Importantly, the effect concerns overall exposure to political news rather than reliance on any specific media type, suggesting that skeptical trust is more associated sustained engagement with political information – and less with a particular news medium.

The individual media pluralism index, on the other hand, exhibits a negative association with compliant and skeptical trust (–0.046 to –0.085) and is positively linked to cynicism (0.113). This finding suggests that diverse media sources may expose citizens to competing cues and critical narratives that, in turn, increase ambiguity of evaluations, thereby amplifying cynical mistrust. In this sense, individual media pluralism may operate differently from system-level media pluralism: while pluralistic media systems can support greater information availability and accountability of political actors and institutions, highly diversified individual media repertoires may instead increase exposure to contradictory evaluations of political actors and institutions. This interpretation is consistent with studies on high-choice media environments and audience fragmentation, which suggest that expanded media choice can diversify exposure but also weaken shared interpretive frameworks within the political information environment (Prior, 2007; Van Aelst et al., 2017; Fletcher & Nielsen, 2018).

Perceptions of media also emerge as strong predictors. Trust in media, perception of media as independent and impartial, and belief in one's own capacity to navigate the information environment exhibit robust, positive associations with compliant trust (0.130 to 0.404). Mistrust of media, perception of media as biased and dependent on elites, and perceived lack of one's media literacy are congruent with the cynical trust type (–0.075 to –0.390). Perceptions of media exhibit no significant association with skeptical (mis)trust type, suggesting this type is not generated by confidence in the credibility of the information environment itself. Substantively, media trust seems to explain whether citizens are inclined toward confidence or cynicism, but it does not explain whether the trust judgement is skeptical that is conditional on careful evaluation of institutional trustworthiness. As such, trust in media appears to operate as a legitimacy heuristic shortcut: citizens who regard the media as trustworthy and impartial are more likely to grant the political institutions the benefit of the doubt (Tsfati & Ariely, 2014; Hanitzsch et al., 2018). Similarly, the models also reveal positive association between generalized social trust and compliant trust (0.111), a negative association between generalized trust and cynical trust type (–0.143), and no association with skeptical (mis)trust type. This suggests that skeptical (mis)trust type is not generated through “spillover” effect from other trust types as broader orientations of confidence or suspicion and instead is largely independent of such predispositions. This suggest that skeptical mis(trust) is a distinct form of political judgement, rather than an intermediate position between compliant trust and cynicism.

Table 2. Effects of media on types of political trust judgements.

		M5 Skeptical Trust	M6 Compliant Trust	M7 Cynical (Mis)Trust
Level 2	World Press Freedom Index	0.003 (0.004)	-0.031*** (0.005)	0.028*** (0.005)
	Newspapers (frequency)	0.008 (0.010)	0.032*** (0.012)	-0.049*** (0.013)
	Television (frequency)	0.052*** (0.011)	0.055*** (0.013)	-0.095*** (0.013)
Level 1:	Radio (frequency)	0.002 (0.010)	0.038*** (0.012)	-0.029** (0.012)
Individual media consumption patterns	Online Social Media (frequency)	0.011 (0.010)	-0.017 (0.012)	0.017 (0.013)
	Online Websites (frequency)	0.010 (0.011)	-0.003 (0.013)	0.007 (0.014)
	Log (Media Exposure, mins)	0.044*** (0.013)	0.025 (0.017)	-0.033** (0.016)
	Media Pluralism Index (1-10)	-0.085*** (0.016)	-0.046** (0.019)	0.114*** (0.022)
Attitudes and perceptions about media	Media Trust Index (1-10)	0.003 (0.009)	0.405*** (0.011)	-0.390*** (0.011)
	Media Impartiality Index (1-10)	-0.015* (0.009)	0.357*** (0.012)	-0.345*** (0.012)
	Media Literacy Index (1-10)	-0.076*** (0.012)	0.129*** (0.016)	-0.076*** (0.016)
Individual level controls: sociodemographic groups, cognitive Resources	Age	-0.002** (0.001)	0.004*** (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)
	Male (ref. female)	-0.016 (0.027)	-0.172*** (0.032)	0.186*** (0.035)
	Urban (ref. rural)	-0.115*** (0.027)	0.129*** (0.032)	0.007 (0.035)
	Income	0.014** (0.005)	-0.039*** (0.006)	0.030*** (0.007)
	Education: medium (ref. low)	0.055 (0.038)	-0.091** (0.044)	0.015 (0.048)
	Education: high (ref. low)	0.140*** (0.042)	-0.321*** (0.050)	0.139** (0.054)
	Position on Left-Right Scale	-0.057*** (0.006)	0.071*** (0.007)	-0.011 (0.007)
	Civic Knowledge	0.066*** (0.013)	-0.002 (0.015)	-0.082*** (0.017)
	Interest in Politics	-0.096*** (0.019)	0.116*** (0.024)	-0.015 (0.024)
	Generalized Social Trust	0.004 (0.006)	0.111*** (0.007)	-0.143*** (0.007)

Note. Entries are log-odds coefficients from mixed-effects logistic regression models, with standard errors in parentheses. Number of countries = 24; N = 24768 in all models. Model statistics are as follows: M5, log likelihood = -16,638.397, Wald $\chi^2(21) = 312.13$, random-intercept variance = 0.035, LR $\chi^2(1) = 147.66$; M6, log likelihood = -12,487.513, Wald $\chi^2(21) = 4,063.30$, random-intercept variance = 0.066, LR $\chi^2(1) = 191.64$; M7, log likelihood = -11,068.716, Wald $\chi^2(21) = 4,070.03$, random-intercept variance = 0.040, LR $\chi^2(1) = 91.08$. * $p < .10$, ** $p < .05$, *** $p < .001$.

Finally, several predictors that can be altogether described as individual level “cognitive resources” exhibit meaningful associations with trust types, although they do not operate uniformly. Tertiary education is positively associated with skeptical (mis)trust (0.140) and cynical mistrust (0.139) judgements and exhibits a negative association with compliant trust (−0.321). This suggests education weakens deference to authority, but the resulting critical disposition can take different forms, including both skepticism and wholesale cynicism. While consistent with the critical citizen argument, it adds an important distinction: critical orientations are not normatively equivalent, and feature both skeptical form congruent with democratic accountability and corrosive cynicism that does not necessarily translate into constructive sanctioning (Norris, 1999; Dalton, 2004; Rosanvallon, 2008). Civic knowledge (0.066) increases the probability of the skeptical type, while exhibiting negative association with compliant trust and cynical mistrust. This suggests civic knowledge, rather than formal education is the cognitive resource most closely associated with skeptical trust. If education appears to create critical distance from authority in general, civic knowledge seems to provide the substantive foundation on which trust judgement can be developed. skeptical (mis)trust therefore is dependent on both the capacity to think critically and on knowledge about political system and how it operates.

Media literacy index yields a more complex pattern. Higher media literacy reduces cynical mistrust (−0.075) but increases compliant trust (0.130) and lowers skeptical (mis)trust (−0.075). Therefore, rather than fostering skeptical evaluation, media competence seems to enhance confidence in mediated information and thereby reinforces institutional support. While media literacy is often expected to foster critical scrutiny of political information and to improve citizens’ ability to identify misinformation (Kahne & Bowyer, 2017; Jones-Jang et al., 2021; Vraga & Tully, 2021), one possible interpretation for the counter-association observed is that media literacy was measured based on self-evaluations by the respondents. Following this logic, those citizens who feel more capable of distinguishing reliable information from fake news become somewhat less prone to generalized suspicion – which, however, does not immediately translate into skeptical trust.

Conclusions

By comparing the implications of mediated political information on the level of political trust and the types of trust judgement, the analysis points out that confidence-advancing mechanisms are not necessarily accountability-fostering ones. Consequently, the democratic value of media influence cannot be inferred from its effect on trust levels alone; it depends on whether media exposure and media evaluations promote performance-responsive skeptical judgement rather than compliant confidence or generalized cynicism.

The introduced residual-based typology of political trust judgements demonstrates that media influence not only how much citizens trust, but also the foundation of the trust judgement and how trust is related to the observable institutional performance. Findings suggest that traditional media use increases the probability of compliant trust and reduces the cynical mistrust type, but, except for television, shows no association with the skeptical type. The duration of exposure increases the likelihood of skeptical trust and reduces the cynical type. A reliance on multiple information sources, on the other hand, strengthens cynicism and undermines skeptical or complaint trust. Perceptions of media, such as trust in media and media impartiality, strengthen compliant trust and reduce cynical mistrust, but again show no significant association with skeptical trust.

Importantly, our findings suggest that skeptical trust is not generated through a “spillover” effect from social trust, neither it is built on confidence in media as a heuristic shortcut. The skeptical trust type is independent from the influence of diffuse trusting orientations towards the society, media,

or the political system as a whole. Instead, it relies more heavily on individual cognitive resources and sustained information exposure, which result in more balanced, skeptical assessment of political actors and institutions. Not less importantly, various media sources and perceptions about media emerge as crucial factors in forming that depart from observable institutional performance, either through overly critical mistrust or exaggerated confidence. These findings further refine the theoretical distinction between trust levels and trust judgments: media sources and media environments do not simply increase or decrease the level of public trust. Instead, they influence the nature and foundation of these judgements that is, whether citizens' trust judgments are responsive to institutional performance and thus can serve as a valid tool in accountability mechanism or being detached from it. The use of traditional media and a media exposure appear to stabilize the democratic legitimacy by reducing cynicism; however, they do not automatically promote the performance-based accountability. In this sense, skeptical trust judgements appear less a product of media environment and more as a function of political knowledge and educational resources.

The findings also suggest that media influence on political trust is best understood as a sequential process rather than as a direct effect of exposure. The two-stage model proposed in this paper distinguishes between the conditions under which political information reaches citizens and the conditions under which it becomes incorporated into trust judgements. At the level of aggregate trust, the evaluation stage appears dominant. However, at the level of trust judgements, these same factors mainly reduce cynicism or reinforce compliance, whereas skeptical trust is linked more clearly to sustained political information exposure and cognitive resources. The model therefore shows that the reception of political information and the evaluation of its credibility are not only sequential steps in one trust-producing process but are associated with different normative forms of political trust.

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Appendix

Table A1. Multilevel benchmark model predicting political trust.

Predictor	Coefficient (SE)
Level 2: Country characteristics	
WGI governance index (2021–2024)	1.340*** (0.174)
Average annual real GDP growth (2021–2024)	0.025 (0.056)
Level 1: Individual characteristics	
Age	-0.005*** (0.001)
Gender (ref: male)	0.249*** (0.025)
Education: Secondary (ref: primary)	0.057 (0.035)
Education: Tertiary (ref: primary)	0.379*** (0.039)
Income: Medium (ref: low)	0.253*** (0.031)
Income: High (ref: low)	0.460*** (0.035)
Constant	3.536*** (0.303)
Observations (Level-1)	24,768
Countries (Level-2)	24

Model statistics: Log likelihood = -59,626.732; Wald $\chi^2(8) = 641.47$, $p < .001$; LR test vs. linear model: $\chi^2 = 725.91$, $p < .001$. Notes: The dependent variable is the aggregated political trust index. The model is a two-level linear mixed-effects regression with random intercepts at country level. Predicted values from this are used to estimate expected political trust and construct the residual-based typology of trust judgements. Reference categories are female, low education, and low income. Coefficients are unstandardized. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Media Exposure: Types. In the TRUEDEM survey, respondents were asked: “People learn what is happening in this country and the world from various sources. For each of the following traditional or online sources, please indicate how often you use it to learn news about politics...”. Responses were recorded on a 1-6 ordinal scale varying from “rarely or never” to “many times a day”. Answers distribution reveals substantive variation in media use profiles. Social media, online news websites, and television emerge as the most frequently used sources for learning about political news (40-45% use daily each). In contrast, radio and especially newspapers are characterized by less frequent use. Each source is included individually in the models.

Media Exposure: Duration. The TRUEDEM survey measures overall exposure to political news through all media sources combined. The respondents were asked: “On a typical day, how much time do you spend watching, reading, or listening to news about politics and current affairs?” Responses were recorded in hours and minutes; this data was then converted into a single aggregated duration of exposure in minutes per day. This measure captures the total duration of daily contact with political information, irrespective of the specific platform or format (textual/ audio/ visual). Country means vary from 83-84 minutes on average in Croatia and Slovenia to over 130 minutes a day on average in Italy and Romania. The grand mean across the pooled 24 countries sample is 111 minutes. Notably, median values are substantially lower than means in all countries, pointing to right-skewness of distributions even after top-coding.

Media Pluralism Index. The concept of media pluralism at the individual level captures the diversity of regularly used sources of political news and reflects the structural breadth of citizens’ information environments. Empirically, in our analysis media pluralism is operationalized as the number of news sources used at least several times a week (categories 4-6 on the frequency scale).

Measured across five media sources (television, newspapers, radio, online news websites, and social media), the index yields a count ranging from 0 (if none of the sources is used several times a week, daily or many times a day) to 5 (if all sources are used at least several times a week or more often).

Media Trust Index. In the present study, trust in news media is operationalized as a composite index capturing generalized confidence in major news provider types, including public service broadcasters; commercial or privately owned broadcasters; print media; and social media. Trust in each item was measured on a 4-point ordinal scale ranging from 1 (“not at all”) to 4 (“completely”). The index is calculated as the arithmetic mean of the available items for each respondent. While public vs commercial broadcasters, printed media and social media do exhibit varying levels of public trust, combining them in an aggregated index allows assessment of the overarching evaluation of trustworthiness of mediated political information. Cronbach’s alpha is 0.747.

Media Impartiality Index. Media impartiality is operationalized as an aggregate index constructed from five items capturing respondents’ assessment of the extent to which news media in their country operate independently from the government on the one hand, and business elites on the other, and whether they provide neutral and accurate coverage. The index draws on agreement ratings for the following statements: *“the government often censors the news media”*; *“independent journalism is widely available”*; *“the news media is in the pocket of rich owners”*; *“most news is politically biased”*; and *“most news is impartial and accurate”*. The perceived impartiality measure is calculated as an arithmetic mean of the five harmonized items and then linearly rescaled to a 1-10 scale, consistent with other attitudinal indices used in the analysis. The scale consistency test yields a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.659.

Media Literacy Index. Respondent’s media literacy is operationalized as a Media Literacy Index constructed from five individual statements that refer to respondent’s self-perceived competence when dealing with mediated information and orientation to political information. Specifically, the included items ask: *“How well informed do you feel you are about politics and current affairs in your country?”*; *“How well informed do you feel you are about politics and current affairs in the European Union?”*; *“I often learn a lot from online sources of information”*; *“I am confident that I can tell real news from fake news”*; and *“I trust information from family, friends and neighbors more than the news media”*. The index is calculated as the arithmetic mean of the five items and rescaled to 1-10 scale, consistent with other measurements in the model. Two important features are inherent to the media literacy index in this study. First, the adopted conceptualization of media literacy is quite broad and extends beyond the narrower performance-based definition of media skills. In this case, media literacy encompasses perceived political informedness, capacity to distinguish fake news, orientation towards professional journalism over information sources among the other. In this framework, media literacy is therefore a multidimensional informational resource that reflects how individuals perceive their own capacity to acquire, evaluate, and appropriately source political information. Secondly, like all other measurements in the model, the index is based on self-assessment and therefore captures subjective evaluations, subject to social desirability bias. The scale consistency test yields a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.625.

By comparing the implications of mediated political information on the level of political trust and the types of trust judgement, the analysis points out that confidence-advancing mechanisms are not necessarily accountability-fostering ones. Consequently, the democratic value of media influence cannot be inferred from its effect on trust levels alone; it depends on whether media exposure and media evaluations promote performance-responsive skeptical judgement rather than compliant confidence or generalized cynicism.

Figure A1. Distribution of political trust judgments by country.

Notes: Trust judgment types are derived from standardized residuals of a multilevel trust–performance regression model. K-means cluster analysis ($k = 3$) was applied to classify respondents into skeptical, compliant, and cynical categories based on deviations from expected trust levels. Percentages are calculated within countries. $N = 24768$ respondents across 24 countries.

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